

Review of the Impact of Dietary Salt on Hypertension and Cardiovascular Health

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Abstract:

Salt has been important in the human diet since the earliest times. However, increases in the availability and consumption of dietary salt have raised concerns that excessive intake may cause hypertension. It is a condition where excessive salt intake leads to elevated blood pressure. This phenomenon occurs when the body regulator mechanism of sodium balance is impaired. Recent research has linked salt intake to variations in blood pressure, but definitive conclusions have been lacking. A reduction in dietary sodium not only decreases blood pressure and the incidence of hypertension but is also associated with a reduction in morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular disease. Among the topics, we examine the effects of salt on fluid and electrolyte homeostasis, the mechanism of salt induced hypertension, the role of salt in experimental hypertension, Mechanism based approaches to prevent salt induced hypertension, and preventing salt sensitivity by increasing potassium intake. Nevertheless, many of these complexities are now well understood and summarised in this review.

Keywords: *Salt intake; Dietary salt; Hypertension; Cardiovascular*

1. INTRODUCTION

Instructed a large group of normotensive individuals to reduce sodium intakes from 68 mmol/day to 157 mmol/day for 12 weeks (Martin Muntzel & Tilman Prueke et al., 2014). The importance of salt in hypertension has been emphasized for years, first by Ambard & Beaujard in 1904 and later by Allen, 1925 and Meneely, 1961. There is considerable evidence to support the hypothesis that essential hypertension frequently is the result of the ingestion of salt. High-salt diets are estimated to cause approximately one-third of cases of hypertension and at least 1 million deaths per year from cardiovascular (CV) events related to salt-induced increases in blood pressure. Hypertension is not only the most common chronic disease worldwide but also a leading cause of death and a risk factor for stroke, ischemic heart disease, heart failure and chronic renal failure (Mozaffarian et al., 2014).

Antihypertensive therapies that manage to be effective in the control of blood pressure (BP) can prevent these complications (Kearney et al., 2005). Blood pressure lowering effects of targeted lifestyle modifications, a cornerstone for the prevention of hypertension and also important for its treatment, are highlighted in hypertension guidelines (Gu, Burt et al., 2012 and Mancia et al., 2013). Proper lifestyle changes, particularly dietary sodium reduction, contribute to BP control in patients already on medical therapy, allowing the reduction of antihypertensive agents (Beaglehole et al., 2011). While there is a significant quantity of evidence linking high-salt intake and increased blood pressure (Eckel et al., 2014), the precise mechanisms that explain their association are not yet fully understood. In healthy subjects, the volume of extracellular fluid (VECF) is maintained within narrow limits despite a wide range of dietary intake of salt and water. The relationship of VECF (particularly the intravascular volume) to overall vascular capacitance determines mean arterial blood pressure and left ventricular filling volume. In the setting of

normal osmoregulation, extracellular sodium content is the primary determinant of VECF. Overall sodium homeostasis depends on the balance between sodium intake and renal and extrarenal losses (Cook et al., 2007). In any given steady state, total daily sodium intake and excretion are equal, and the total quantity of sodium determines the VECF. According to Guyton, if blood pressure rises above the pressure natriuresis equilibrium point, sodium and water excretion will become greater than intake, decreasing blood pressure towards previous levels. In salt sensitive subjects, the pressure natriuresis relationship is shifted to the right, and higher blood pressure levels are necessary to achieve an increase in sodium excretion. Higher blood pressure levels are needed to maintain sodium balance (Skorecki et al., 2008). Not all individuals, whether normotensive or hypertensive, have the same susceptibility to the effects of salt. The blood pressure sensitivity to salt is the inter-individual differences in the blood pressure response to changes in dietary salt intake (Guyton et al., 1990). The purpose of this review is to summarize the current understanding of the various pathophysiological mechanisms potentially involved in determining the salt sensitive phenotype. Genetic, neuronal, and immune alterations are reviewed. Additionally, we provide an update on the current knowledge of a new approach proposing that the interstitium of the skin may act as a sodium reservoir. However, it is well known that the degree of blood pressure (BP) sensitivity to salt intake differs among patients with essential hypertension (Luft et al., 1997). The causative factors of salt-sensitive essential hypertension vary and may interact with each other (Fujita et al., 1984 and Fujita & Ando, 1984). Moreover, aging (Luft et al., 1997) changes in body weight (Ando & Fujita., 2012) and other attributes alter the salt sensitivity of BP (Guyton., 1992). Americans demonstrate an increased prevalence of salt sensitivity and the discovery of hypertension-related genes that regulate sodium reabsorption in the kidney (Lambers, Heerspink et al., 2012). Salt sensitivity refers to the physiological trait present in mammals by which the blood pressure (BP) on the population exhibits changes parallel to changes in salt intake (Elijovich, Weinberger et al., 2016).

2. LOW SODIUM INTAKE AND CARDIOVASCULAR RISK

Over the years, the evidence of a close relationship between high sodium intake and hypertension leading to increased cardiovascular risk and mortality has become increasingly consolidated. For this reason, we are used to considering that the lower the sodium intake is, the better the patient's prognosis is. However, the studies that are beginning to shake the foundations of this historic fortress are growing in number. Actually, in the analysis of this topic, several cohort studies (Thomas et al., 2011 and Saulnier et al., 2014) and meta-analyses (Mente et al., 2016 and Graudal et al., 2014) have shown that the relationship between sodium intake and poor patient prognosis have not a linear trend, but rather describe a J-shape curve. In these studies, an increased risk not only in high sodium intake but also in significantly low sodium intake levels is underlined. To reach this declaration, large patient populations have been studied, including various types of healthy patients or those with different co-morbidities (i.e., diabetes, vascular disease, hypertension population), with wide numbers in all subgroups.

The relationship between cardiovascular events and sodium intake was derived from baseline urinary sodium excretion on a 24h urine collection. Urinary sodium excretion of less than 3 g/day is considered to reflect a low sodium dietary intake. It was observed that a poor patient prognosis is associated with either a very high or a very low 24h urinary sodium excretion. This relationship does not depend on BP, aging, diabetes, chronic kidney disease, or cardiovascular disease (Mente et al., 2016), who reported that only patients with arterial hypertension have a high cardiovascular risk associated with high sodium intake, while this association was not confirmed in patients

without hypertension

Mechanisms linking high sodium intake and cardiovascular adverse events are well known; less defined are those that justify a relationship between low salt intake and high mortality. Sodium is an indispensable cation, essential to the action potential of all cells in the body, and its homeostasis is under tight physiological regulation. Sodium intake is governed by neural mechanisms that regulate the intake of sodium and related homeostatic systems, and so although extreme reductions in sodium intake are possible in controlled settings for short periods, this is unlikely to be sustainable in everyday life in the long term. Thus, as for all our body components, there may be an optimal range for its intake, below which the human body starts being damaged, at variance from what happens in case of intake of, or exposure to, potentially toxic external substances, such as tobacco smoke, drugs or environmental pollutants.

In experimental models, it is known that sodium restriction results in increased atherosclerosis (Catanozi et al., 2003). In humans, the relationship between salt restriction and increased renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system activation has been described (Graudal et al., 1998 and Brunner et al., 1972) as well as the relationship with increased sympathetic activity (Grassi et al., 2002) and insulin resistance (Petrie et al., 1998; Garg et al., 2011 and Nakandakare et al., 2008). High renin concentrations and increased levels of catecholamines have been reported in studies in poor sodium intake populations. On the other hand, several studies have shown that increases in renin, aldosterone, and catecholamines are all associated with increased cardiovascular disease events and mortality (Grassi et al., 2002 and Grassi et al., 1997). Regarding sympathetic activity, sodium intake restriction is associated with a persistent attenuation of the muscle sympathetic nerve activity responses to baroreceptor stimulation and de Furthermore, there is a significant correlation between the reduction in baroreflex sensitivity and the increase of concomitant muscle sympathetic nerve activity. Accordingly, a reduced ability of this reflex to obtain a proper downregulation of sympathetic tone leads to the sympatho-stimulating effect of a very low sodium intake. As described in other studies evaluating high sodium intake, the increase in muscle sympathetic nerve traffic due to very low sodium intake is also associated with an increase in plasma norepinephrine, and a drastic reduction in sodium intake has been reported to cause, in man, an increase in renal norepinephrine removal. Moreover, sodium restriction causes insulin resistance; this may be the result of sympathetic activation, but, in turn, increased insulin levels may themselves have a sympatho-excitatory influence. Lastly, a low salt supply causes a reduction of central venous pressure, which may lead to an activation of the sympathetic system via the unloading of cardiopulmonary receptors.

To sum up, predicting the net clinical effect of low sodium intake based on only considering the effects of sodium on BP might not provide a comprehensive view of its effects on cardiovascular disease and mortality, especially within the range of sodium intake that affects the renin system (<4 g/day). In other words, the effects of sodium intake level on clinical outcomes are only partly mediated through its effects on BP. For a full understanding of the clinical impact of sodium intake, it is also necessary to consider other mechanisms that might be at play. In particular, while the potential harm of sodium excess may be BP-driven, the potential negative effects of a low sodium intake may be mediated by elevated renin-aldosterone activity and sympathetic neural activation. Numerous methodological concerns have arisen from studies that have underlined the J-shape of sodium intake and cardiovascular events (Cook et al., 2014 and Batuman et al., 2014). It has been remarked that a single morning urine sample may offer an inaccurate measure of usual sodium intake, ignoring day-to-day variability in sodium intake, diurnal variation in sodium excretion, and the effects of medications. Another confounder could come from the fact that other

prognostically negative factors might be activated in the low sodium intake interval because of dietary advice or poor appetite, or in the high sodium intake interval because of concomitant high caloric intake (typical of overweight or diabetic patients), which could have contributed to increased mortality in the low- and the high-sodium groups respectively (reverse causality). Although more studies have confirmed the benefit of reducing sodium intake in hypertensive subjects with a high salt intake, it is unclear whether the remaining more than 90% of the population will profit from dietary sodium reduction. Therefore, until new robust data emerge from large trials, it might be prudent to recommend a reduction in sodium intake only in those with high sodium intake and hypertension. (Grassi et al., 1997).

3. SALT AND HYPERTENSION

The relationship between salt consumption and increased BP is based on strong experimental and epidemiological data. Lewis Dahl was the first one to breed rat strains exclusively SS or SR, and he highlighted the role of the kidney in the physiology of arterial hypertension, by transplanting kidneys from SR rat donors into SS hypertensive recipients, BP became normal for recipients and vice versa (Dahl and Heine et al., 1975). The same was later demonstrated in hypertensive patients receiving renal transplantation from non-hypertensive donors (Curtis et al., 1983), and the doctrine that “blood pressure follows the kidney” was established. Increased salt intake in salt-sensitive rats increases BP compared with salt resistance but also causes organ damage regardless of hypertension, such as heart hypertrophy, vascular hypertrophy, and nephrosclerosis (Zicha et al., 2012). The high-salt diet reduces the survival of mice in proportion to the NaCl content (Meneely and Ball, 1958). Denton monitored BP for 20 months in two groups of chimpanzees. In one group, the diet was very low in sodium (30 mmol), while in the other, it was 130 mmol. In the latter, systolic and diastolic BP increased. This change was completely overturned when the diet was salt restricted again for 6 months (Denton et al., 1995). In a Dutch study, 476 newborns were randomized at birth to be fed commercial formula milk or low sodium milk (6.3 mmol/L) for 6 months, and the BP decreased by 2.1 mmHg compared with the control group. Fifteen years later, 167 adolescents from this study were evaluated, and it was striking that those who had been fed with low sodium milk continued to have 3.6 mmHg systolic BP and 2.2 mm diastolic BP Hg lower than adolescents control group (Geleijnse et al., 1997).

The first epidemiological study that established the association between BP and salt was the International Study of Electrolyte Excretion and Blood Pressure (INTERSALT) study. This multicentre observational study included 10,000 men and women aged 20–59 years in 32 countries and concluded that for every 10 mEq increase in sodium intake, systolic BP increased by 0.9 mmHg, and diastolic BP by 0.45 mmHg. There was a more significant correlation between sodium excretion and changes in BP with age (Increase in salt consumption by 6 g/day over a 30-year period, increases the BP by 9 mmHg) (Stamler et al., 1989 and Elliott et al., 1989). BP levels did not increase with age in just four communities that lived primitively with diets of very low salt content (Na excretion <60 mEq/24 h). Such a tribe is Yanomami, who live in the forests of Venezuela and retain very low BP throughout their life due to very low salt intake. On the contrary, their neighbouring Yekwana tribe has been exposed to Western lifestyles, and their BP is comparatively more elevated and increases proportionally to age (Mueller et al., 2018). Data from a study in 66 countries (74% of the total world adult population) in 2010 showed that average sodium consumption is 3.95 g per day with a range of 2.18–5.51 g. This study found that 1.65 million deaths from cardiovascular (CV) causes were due to a daily intake of more than 2.0 g sodium, while a reduction of 1.75 g sodium per day reduces systolic BP/ diastolic BP by 4.2/2.1

mmHg, respectively, (5.4/2.8) mmHg in hypertensive patients (Mozaffarian et al., 2014).

The relationship between salt consumption and total CV mortality is not clear, especially regarding low salt diets. In a study gathering data from around 102,000 patients from 17 countries, sodium consumption of more than 7 g per day increased the risk of CV and total mortality by 1.15 times compared with baseline (4–6.99 g of sodium). This relationship was stronger for hypertensive patients and for those consuming more than 6 g per day. However, this study showed that consumption of less than 3 g of sodium per day was also associated with an increased risk of CV events by 1.27 times compared with baseline (Donnell et al., 2016). Essentially, the relationship between salt intake and CV morbidity is a J-curve relationship and not proportional (Mente et al., 2016), especially in non-hypertensive populations. These findings triggered a heated discussion in the literature on whether salt consumption guidelines should be changed in the general population with particular attention to reduced salt intake (Donnell et al., 2016). Despite recent studies that confirmed the same J-curve (Mente et al., 2018), the guidelines of cardiology and hypertension societies on both sides of the Atlantic (American Heart Association and European Society of Hypertension) recommend sodium intake <2 g per day (Williams et al., 2018).

4. MECHANISM OF SALT INDUCED HYPERTENSION

It is tempting to make the jump from inherited hypertension-prone rats to humans with essential hypertension. We can formulate the following hypothesis: Many humans are not able to handle large amounts of salt in their diet. The salt habit is of comparatively recent origin in our history. The daily ingestion of large amounts of salt leads to a chronically expanded extracellular volume. The latter acts as a considerable stress on the functional capacity of the kidney, and as the individual ages renal competency declines and blood pressure begins to rise. It is the only positive feedback mechanism available to prevent edema. By contrast, the renin-angiotensin mechanism is designed mostly to conserve rather than enhance salt loss. However, such a negative feedback mechanism is severely limited as opposed to a positive feedback mechanism, which has infinite gain.

An additional facet of this hypothesis is that renal functional capacity to handle an excess volume is not uniformly distributed in the population. It varies from individual to individual as an inherited characteristic. It is distributed in the same unimodal way that blood pressure is distributed in the population. The individuals who are so unfortunate as to have kidneys with a poor functional capacity to excrete salt are destined to develop hypertension if exposed to a daily intake of salted foods: salt sensitive hypertension. Those with a high functional capacity to excrete salt and water loads will maintain normal diastolic blood pressure throughout their lifetimes: salt resistant hypertension (Murphy., 1950 and Watkin et al., 1950).

4.1. A vasoconstriction theory of salt sensitivity

It has been reported that in some cases of salt-induced hypertension, increases in blood pressure are initiated by increases in vascular resistance in the absence of increases in cardiac output or even with decreases in cardiac output. For example, Obst and colleagues studied unilaterally nephrectomized mice during the induction of hypertension by subcutaneous administration of deoxycorticosterone acetate (DOCA) and provision of a 1% NaCl solution to drink. Cardiac output measured with a Doppler flow probe around the ascending aorta did not increase during the induction of the DOCA-NaCl hypertension (Obst et al., 2004). In studies of the initiation of mineralocorticoid hypertension in dogs, pigs, and sheep, the hemodynamic pattern has been

variable. In some animals, the hemodynamic pattern in response to salt loading is consistent with the vaso-dysfunction theory (Ueno et al., 1988 and Bravo et al., 1977). In other animals, the induction of salt-dependent hypertension is better explained by a vasoconstriction theory in which the increases in blood pressure are initiated by increases in vascular resistance with little or no increase in cardiac output or even a decrease in cardiac output (Pan et al., 1982). These studies provide no evidence for the historical theory of salt sensitivity that initiation of salt-induced increases in blood pressure requires abnormally large increases in cardiac output (Guyton., 1990; Guyton., 1980; Hall et al., 1990 and Hall et al., 1996). In addition, recent studies challenge the concept that salt-dependent hypertension is sustained by increases in cardiac output that are too small to be detected (Guyton et al., 1980; Guyton., 1995; Hall., 2016 and Guyton., 1987). For example, in studies by Ball and colleagues in which blood pressure was increased by the administration of aldosterone and a high-salt diet, cardiac output was found to be decreased in the established phase of hypertension (Ball et al., 2017).

4.2. Mechanism-based approaches to prevent salt-induced hypertension

According to the vaso-dysfunction theory, the induction of salt-induced hypertension often involves the combination of normal salt-induced increases in sodium balance and cardiac output (similar to those observed in normal salt-resistant controls) together with subnormal vasodilation and abnormal levels of vascular resistance. In such cases, initiation of salt-induced hypertension could be prevented by either (1) preventing the abnormal vascular resistance responses to increases in salt intake (preventing vaso-dysfunction) or (2) preventing the normal increases in sodium balance and cardiac output induced by increases in salt intake. We suggest that interventions to prevent salt-induced hypertension primarily focus on preventing the abnormal physiologic mechanisms that appear to commonly mediate salt sensitivity, i.e., preventing the abnormal vascular resistance responses to salt loading that are usually required for initiation of salt-induced increases in blood pressure (Kurtz and Morris, 2017). This raises the related questions: (1) in normal salt-resistant humans, what are the common mechanisms that mediate vasodilation and decreases in vascular resistance in response to increases in salt intake and (2) in salt-sensitive humans with normal blood pressure (Morris et al., 2016; Brooks and Osborn., 1995 and Kitiyakara, 2003)

5. SALT SENSITIVE TO BLOOD PRESSURE

There is no consensus on a definition of salt sensitivity (Fujita et al., 2014; Rodriguez-iturbe et al., 2007 and Romero et al., 2007). A significant increase in blood pressure following a salt loading

is included in all definitions; those in whom the effect of a salt loaded state is arbitrarily high are called “salt sensitive” because of their exaggerated response to sodium. The different schemes range from sudden (within hours) sodium loading and depletion to long term (weeks) protocols (Sullivan et al., 1991). In addition, no agreement exists on the degree of blood pressure change necessary to classify an individual as salt-sensitive (Sullivan et al., 1991). So far, one of the most common methods was described by Weinberger in 1986, who standardised a protocol of rapid intravascular volume expansion and contraction for investigative purposes. He measured BP after an intravenous infusion of 2 L of normal (0.9%) saline and after sodium and volume depletion induced by a low sodium diet and furosemide administration in 378 normal volunteers and 198 subjects with essential hypertension. Those in whom mean arterial blood pressure decreased by at least 10 mmHg after sodium and volume depletion were considered sodium-sensitive, and those with a decrease of 5 mmHg or less (including an increase in pressure) were considered sodium-resistant. Follow-up studies have demonstrated that a salt sensitive state is reproducible and that salt sensitive normotensive individuals become hypertensives more than those who are not (Weinberger et al., 1986). In a different approach, some authors have developed mathematical models to define salt sensitivity. A computational model called the “neurogenic model” has been proposed recently, where several potential regulators operate in parallel to regulate sodium excretion; this model also assumes a pressure independent natriuresis, as opposed to the Guyton model (Weinberger et al., 1991). Conceptually, Fujita defines BP sensitivity as the inter-individual difference in BP in response to changes in dietary sodium chloride intake (Fujita et al., 2014).

6. SYSTEMIC REGULATION OF SALT AND BLOOD PRESSURE SENSITIVE HYPERTENSION

The aldosterone-mineralocorticoid receptor (MR) pathway and the sympathetic nervous system (SNS) have a central role in short-term and also long-term blood pressure control. Animal studies provided evidence that serum- and glucocorticoid-inducible kinase 1 (SGK1), a downstream mediator of mineralocorticoid receptors (MRs) that activates the epithelial sodium channel (ENaC) in tubules, may play a role in salt adaptation and the pathogenesis of hypertension. In Dahl salt-sensitive hypertensive rats, sodium intake upregulates the expression of SGK1, suggesting that MRs are activated in an aldosterone-independent manner (Farjah et al., 2003). Aldosterone decreased mRNA expression ENaC in Dahl salt-sensitive but not in Dahl salt-resistant rats and elevated SGK1 expression in Dahl salt resistant but not in Dahl salt sensitive rats. These observations indicate that ENaC and SGK1 are abnormally regulated by aldosterone in salt sensitive hypertensive rats, proposing that disturbance of the aldosterone regulation would be one of the factors causing salt-sensitive hypertension (Aoi Niisaton et al., 2007).

The deleterious effect of aldosterone is amplified by salt intake, both augmenting MR activity (Nagase et al., 2007). A high-salt status acts synergistically with aldosterone to activate renal Rac1 (a small GTPase, member of the Rho-guanine triphosphate hydroxylases family) in salt-sensitive hypertension, leading to high blood pressure and renal damage. The crosstalk between MR and Rac1 modulates MR function (Brilla and Weber, 1992) and this paradoxical response of MRs to salt loading in salt sensitive hypertension is attributable to the abnormal response of Rac1 to salt. The inhibition of Rac1 lowers BP and ameliorates tissue damage by reversing the increase in renal Rac1 and MR activity. Thus, Rac1 is an upstream regulator of MRs and serves as a determinant of BP salt sensitivity (Shibata et al., 2011).

In his book “*The Wisdom of the Body*” (1932), Cannon stated that the sympathetic apparatus acts to keep constant the fluid matrix of the body. The targets of the renal sympathetic nerve on the kidney are the juxtaglomerular granular cells (renin secretion, *via* stimulation of β 1-

adrenoceptors); the tubular epithelial cells (increased tubular sodium reabsorption, *via* stimulation of α 1B-adrenoceptors; and the renal vasculature (decreased renal blood flow, *via* stimulation of α 1A-adrenoceptors) (DiBona., 2005). The kidney is not only a target of SNS but is also the origin of afferent sympathetic signaling that modulates the SNS activity. Indeed, changes in renal perfusion pressure or uremic toxins can arouse discharges from renal afferent fibres (Wadei and Textor, 2012).

Animal studies showed that Dahl salt-sensitive rats with a 4% sodium chloride diet developed hypertension and incremented SNS activity; and four weeks after targeted sympathetic ablation, blood pressure was lower compared with sham operated rats (Foss et al., 2013). Also, clinical trials have demonstrated that renal denervation causes substantial blood-pressure reduction in patients with resistant hypertension (Krum et al., 2009). However, renal denervation did not perform better than medical treatment in SIMPLICITY HTN 3.

With-no-lysine kinase 4 (WNK4) plays an important role in salt-sensitive hypertension and sympathetic overstimulation. Under normal conditions, WNK4 inhibits the thiazide-sensitive sodium chloride co-transporter (NCC), resulting in an increased renal sodium excretion. Adrenergic stimulation in salt-loaded models leads to WNK4 downregulation, NCC activation in the distal convoluted tubule, salt retention and increased blood pressure. In deoxycorticosterone acetate (DOCA)-treated rats and Dahl-S rats, salt-induced hypertension was associated with an abnormal response of WNK4 to salt loading. The importance of anomalous β 2-adrenergic (β 2AR) receptor and WNK4 signalling in the pathogenesis of salt-induced hypertension was confirmed by the reversal of decreased WNK4 expression and hypertension after renal denervation, suggesting that the β 2AR-WNK4-NCC pathway is involved in the molecular basis of salt-sensitive hypertension (Mu et al., 2011). The fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF23)-bone-kidney axis is part of a recently described system linking bone to other organ functions through an endocrine network that is integrated with the parathyroid hormone- vitamin D axis and which plays an important role in health and disease (Martin et al., 2012). At physiological concentrations, binding of FGF23 to target cells requires co-expression of Klotho. FGF23 increases in chronic kidney disease (CKD) and is associated with left ventricular hypertrophy, vascular calcifications and mortality in CKD patients (Faul et al., 2011). Andrukhova found that FGF23 signalling in the distal renal tubules includes a cascade involving extracellular signal regulated kinase 1 and 2 (ERK1/2), SGK1, and WNK4 (involved in sodium handling). Interestingly, FGF23 is a direct regulator of sodium chloride co-transporter (NCC) in distal renal tubules, and recent studies identify FGF23 as a sodium conserving hormone. The authors argue that FGF23's role in sodium homeostasis may explain its relationship with cardiovascular risk and mortality in CKD patients. They also state that the link between phosphate and sodium homeostasis may have connotations for the general population because a high dietary phosphate intake might predispose to the development of hypertension (Andrukhova et al., 2014).

7. ROLE OF KIDNEY IN SALT-SENSITIVITY HYPERTENSION

Despite the complex pathophysiology of salt sensitive hypertension, the increase in salt sensitivity is solely attributable to the abnormal function of sodium (Na⁺) excretion in the kidney. Described simply, BP is a product of cardiac output and peripheral vascular resistance. In salt-sensitive hypertension, excess salt induces Na⁺ retention, resulting in a rise in BP due to an increase in cardiac output. These acute hemodynamic changes are chronically altered, possibly due to whole body autoregulation, resulting in increased vascular resistance (Guyton et al., 1992). However, initial retention of Na⁺ is critical for the salt-induced increase in BP. According to Guyton's

model, the relationship between arterial pressure and renal Na⁺ excretion is shifted to the right in patients with salt-sensitive hypertension, and its slope is less steep than that of normotensive subjects (Hall et al., 1999). This implies that during high salt intake, salt-sensitive hypertensive subjects require higher BP to excrete Na⁺ sufficiently under conditions of abnormal kidney function.

In Dahl salt-sensitive and resistant rats, when inter-strain renal transplants were performed, the change in BP in response to salt loading was largely determined by the genotype of the donor kidney (Dahl et al., 1974). Dahl salt-resistant rats transplanted with the kidney of salt-sensitive rats showed salt-induced increases in BP, whereas salt-sensitive rats transplanted with the kidney of salt-resistant rats did not. Interestingly, compared to that of wild-type mice, the increase in BP induced by angiotensin II (Ang II) infusion was less in mice lacking Ang II type 1 (AT1) receptor in the kidney, but was almost the same as that in mice lacking cardiac and vascular AT1 receptor (Crowley et al., 2006). Because Ang II stimulates Na⁺ reabsorption in proximal tubules (Li, Yamada et al., 2008). These results suggest that salt retention may play an important role in Ang II-induced hypertension. It was also reported that the Ang II-induced increase in BP was attenuated in mice lacking the AT1 receptor in renal proximal tubules (Gurley et al., 2011). Thus, abnormal control of renal Na⁺ reabsorption may play an essential role in the hypertensive effects of Ang II. An abnormal BP set point for kidney Na⁺ excretion can be observed in the development of hypertension by treatment with vasoconstrictor substances such as Ang II, aldosterone, and norepinephrine, components known to participate in renal sympathetic drive (Shibata et al., 2011).

8. PREVENTING SALT SENSITIVITY BY INCREASING POTASSIUM INTAKE

A potassium intake of approximately 3500 mg/day is recommended for adults by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the U.K. National Health Service (NHS). Studies have demonstrated that salt sensitivity can occur in normotensive individuals consuming less than this recommended amount of potassium (Filippini et al., 2020 and Krishna et al., 1989). Increasing potassium intake to above 3500 mg/day (3900–4700 mg/day) with potassium bicarbonate or potassium chloride has been shown to prevent salt-induced increases in blood pressure in these individuals (Krishna et al., 1989 and Siani et al., 1987). This suggests that augmenting potassium intake is a viable strategy for reducing the risk of salt-induced hypertension without necessarily reducing salt intake.

Additionally, the greater salt sensitivity observed in adults who self-identify as black, compared to those who self-identify as white, may be related to lower potassium consumption in black individuals. When potassium intake is near or above the recommended amount by the NHS and WHO, the racial disparity in salt sensitivity is reduced or eliminated (Fujita & Ando, 1984). Supplemental potassium appears to protect against salt sensitivity by enhancing renal excretion of sodium and influencing nitric oxide activity and vascular resistance responses to salt intake (Siani et al., 1987; Filippini et al., 2020; Krishna et al., 1989 and Fujita & Ando, 1984).

Furthermore, high potassium intake can also reduce blood pressure, with its blood pressure-lowering effects being more pronounced at higher levels of salt intake (Filippini et al., 2020). For individuals consuming substantial amounts of salt (7 g/day or more), achieving potassium intakes of approximately 3500 mg/day or more can reduce blood pressure without reducing salt intake (Krishna et al., 1989; Siani et al., 1987; Fujita & Ando., 1984; Iimura et al., 1981 and MacGregor et al., 1982). However, in individuals on low-salt diets (<4.8 g/day), higher potassium intakes (~3500–5000 mg/day) do not significantly reduce blood pressure (Smith et al., 1985 and Grimm et al., 1990). Increasing potassium intake independently of salt intake can have beneficial health

effects (Drewnowski et al., 2015 and Aburto et al., 2013).

The favourable blood pressure effects of supplemental potassium intake in individuals consuming high-salt diets, various government and medical authorities are engaged in educational efforts to promote greater potassium consumption in the general population. However, efforts to increase potassium consumption by encouraging greater intake of fruits and vegetables have met with little success. Median potassium intakes in the U.K. and the U.S.A. remain far below the level recommended by the NHS and the WHO (Drewnowski et al., 2015). Thus, there is ongoing interest in methods to augment potassium intake that do not depend on increasing the intake of fruits and vegetables. One such method is the use of salt substitutes prepared by adding potassium chloride to sodium chloride.

8.1. Action of Sodium salt & potassium salt

Numerous studies have demonstrated a direct correlation between high sodium intake and hypertension, as well as an inverse relationship between high potassium intake and hypertension (Whelton et al., 2014). Consistently, it has been shown that reducing sodium consumption and increasing potassium intake can lower blood pressure, improve overall physical health, and reduce salt sensitivity (Ellison DH et al., 2021). Therefore, it is recommended to replace sodium salts with potassium salts. Foods rich in potassium include dried fruits like raisins and apricots, lentils, beans, potatoes, spinach, broccoli, avocados, and bananas.

This emphasizes the importance of dietary balance in managing blood pressure and promoting overall health. High sodium intake is linked to elevated blood pressure, while potassium helps relax blood vessels and excrete sodium, thereby lowering blood pressure. Adjusting your diet by incorporating potassium-rich foods can effectively manage blood pressure and contribute to better health.

9. SALT REDUCING STRATEGIES

The Institute of Medicine recommends several strategies to manage sodium intake and combat hypertension. These include public education to raise awareness about the health risks associated with high sodium consumption and individual dietary counselling to offer personalized advice for reducing sodium intake. Food labelling is crucial to ensure clear information about the sodium content of products. Additionally, the food industry is encouraged to voluntarily reduce sodium levels in their products. Government and private sector food procurement policies should also be implemented to ensure that purchased food is lower in sodium. Finally, the FDA is urged to modify the status of sodium as "generally regarded as safe" (GRAS) to enforce stricter regulations. These combined efforts aim to create a comprehensive approach to reducing sodium intake across the population (Cobb et al., 2012).

9.1. Public Education

Public education campaigns have been a long-standing strategy to reduce sodium intake. Since the 1970s, the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute has sponsored efforts like the National Blood Pressure Education Campaign to educate people about reducing sodium. These campaigns successfully increased awareness about the link between sodium and high blood pressure, with public knowledge rising from 12% in 1979 to 48% in 1984. However, maintaining these gains has been difficult. By 2002, awareness dropped to 39%, and only 33% of consumers actively tried to reduce their sodium intake. This could be because many Americans don't understand their sodium consumption. Despite increased awareness, sodium intake has not decreased and may have even

increased since the 1970s (McGuire, 2010).

Public education is one of the simplest strategies to implement. It doesn't need regulatory or legislative action, is relatively inexpensive, and is generally uncontroversial. However, due to the widespread and high levels of sodium in the food supply, reducing sodium consumption will require lower sodium levels in packaged and restaurant foods. While consumer education is valuable for raising awareness and garnering support for broader initiatives, it alone is unlikely to significantly reduce sodium intake.

9.2. Dietary Counselling

Personalized dietary counselling, provided by physicians or other healthcare professionals, is a key approach to lowering sodium intake. Research indicates that significant sodium reduction can be accomplished through dedicated dietary sodium counselling (Whelton et al., 1998). To efficiently guide patients in reducing their dietary salt intake, physicians should stay informed about current public health initiatives. These efforts include national campaigns led by the federal government and professional organizations, as well as local health campaigns focused on sodium reduction. Additionally, sodium has been a topic in popular media, with notable coverage such as the feature article on the highly sought-after cover of the November 2010 issue of Vogue magazine (Cobb et al., 2012). Dietary counselling is very important for high-risk patients. Referrals to a registered dietitian or certified health educator should be made. Medicare and other insurance companies cover dietary counselling for certain patients, like those with chronic kidney disease and diabetes. While it can be hard to change patient behaviour, clinician support is essential to promote public health efforts.

9.3. Food Labelling

Food labelling empowers motivated consumers to select lower sodium products. Additionally, certain types of labelling can encourage manufacturers to reformulate their products to reduce sodium content. These labels have been required since the National Labelling and Education Act was passed in 1990 (McGuire, 2010). Sodium information on labels is presented in a technical format, including milligrams per serving and the percentage (%) daily value of sodium. This information is typically found on the back of packaged food, written in fine print, and surrounded by other nutrition and ingredient details. Consumers often find these labels confusing, particularly those with lower literacy or numeracy skills (Rothman et al., 2017). Recent sodium reduction campaigns aim to encourage the use of labels to reduce intake. However, studies indicate a decline in the overall usage of these labels, especially sodium information. Moreover, individuals who use Nutrition Facts Panels have not shown a reduction in their sodium intake (Variyam et al., 2008).

Food labels assist consumers in selecting packaged foods with lower sodium content, but there is room for improvement in the labelling system. Prominent and consistent labels can effectively influence consumer choices. Moreover, labels highlighting high sodium levels can motivate manufacturers to voluntarily reduce sodium in their products. However, without a decrease in the overall sodium content of packaged foods, even the most effective labelling system will not be enough to significantly reduce sodium intake.

10. ADDITIONAL ADVERSE HEALTH EFFECTS OF SALT

10.1. Kidney Disorder

Many factors that contribute to the progression of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) have been associated with salt intake, including blood pressure (BP), proteinuria, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction (Ritz et al., 2009). There is a direct, dose-dependent relationship between salt intake and urinary albumin excretion (Verhave et al., 2004). Reducing salt intake is crucial for managing the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD) (HE, Tan et al., 2020). High salt intake is linked to several risk factors, including high blood pressure, proteinuria, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction, which contribute to CKD progression. Studies have shown that lowering salt intake significantly reduces 24-hour urinary albumin and protein excretion in individuals with hypertension, diabetes, and CKD. Furthermore, the effectiveness of certain medications, like angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers, is diminished when salt intake is high in patients with proteinuria or diabetes (Swift et al., 2005). Importantly, research suggests that reducing salt intake can help slow down the progression of CKD, highlighting the need for careful dietary management in these patients (Cianciaruso et al., 1998).

10.2. Gastric cancer

Lanfranco D'Elia indicate that high dietary salt intake is associated with an increased risk of gastric cancer, as salt can damage the stomach lining, making it more susceptible to cancer (Lanfranco et al., 2012). Tsugane found that consuming highly salted foods, like salted fish and pickles, increases the risk of gastric cancer due to the harmful effects of salt on the stomach lining (Tsugane et al., 2004). Wong discovered that high salt intake can worsen *Helicobacter pylori* infection, a known risk factor for gastric cancer. The bacteria thrive in the acidic environment created by high salt levels, leading to increased inflammation and damage to the stomach lining. Together, these studies highlight the significant link between salt intake, *Helicobacter pylori* infection, and the increased risk of gastric cancer (Wong et al., 2004).

10.3. Kidney Stones and Bone Density Loss

High salt intake raises the risk of kidney stones by increasing urinary calcium excretion, with calcium being the main component of most urinary stones (Cappuccio et al., 2000). This increase in salt intake creates a negative calcium balance, which triggers compensatory mechanisms to enhance intestinal calcium absorption and mobilize calcium from the bones. Cohort studies have indicated that hip bone density loss in postmenopausal women is linked to their baseline salt intake, and this association is as strong as that related to calcium intake (Devine et al., 1995).

10.4. Excess Weight and Obesity

High salt intake is linked to an increased risk of excess weight and adiposity by raising the consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages (He et al., 2008 and Grimes et al., 2013). Additionally, there is evidence suggesting a direct connection between salt intake and excess weight and/or adiposity, independent of total calorie or sugar-sweetened beverage consumption (Ma, He and Macgregor et al., 2015). Animal studies have indicated that salt intake may directly affect body fat metabolism (Fonseca-Alaniz et al., 2007). Innovative research on long-term sodium homeostasis indicates that high salt intake might trigger energy-intensive mechanisms that lead to muscle mass breakdown (catabolism). This breakdown occurs as the body attempts to regulate the excess sodium. To prevent muscle mass catabolism, the body needs to increase its food (and thus calorie) intake to meet the energy demands of sodium regulation (Kitada et al., 2017). This

highlights the complex relationship between high salt intake, energy balance, and muscle preservation (Rakova et al., 2013).

10.5. Brain Disorders

Several studies in both animals and humans suggest a link between high salt intake and cognitive impairment, as well as Alzheimer's disease, either through its impact on blood pressure or through mechanisms independent of blood pressure (Liu et al., 2014 and Ge, wang et al., 2017). Additionally, randomized trials indicate that reducing dietary salt intake can decrease the risk of headaches (Faraco et al., 2019). These findings highlight the importance of managing salt consumption to support brain health and reduce the occurrence of headaches (Chen et al., 2016 and Amer et al., 2014).

11. WHO REGULATIONS ON SALT REDUCTION

Excessive sodium consumption is linked to approximately 1.89 million deaths annually. High sodium intake is a well-known factor that leads to elevated blood pressure and a higher risk of cardiovascular disease (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2019).

For adults, the WHO advises consuming less than 2000 mg of sodium per day, which is the same as less than 5 grams of salt (just under a teaspoon).

For children aged 2–15 years, the WHO suggests reducing the adult amount based on their energy needs. This advice does not apply to babies who are exclusively breastfed (0–6 months) or those in the complementary feeding stage while still being breastfed (6–24 months).

All salt eaten should be iodized (fortified with iodine), as iodine is crucial for healthy brain development in foetuses and young children, and it helps improve overall mental function.

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified a set of evidence-based "best buy" interventions to combat non-communicable diseases, aiming for quick results in terms of lives saved, healthy life years gained, cases of disease prevented, and costs avoided.

There are four key strategies for reducing sodium intake: reformulating food products to contain less salt and setting target levels for the amount of salt in foods and meals; creating a supportive environment in public institutions like hospitals, schools, workplaces, and nursing homes that provide lower sodium options; implementing clear and informative front-of-pack labelling to help consumers make healthier choices; and running communication and mass media campaigns to change behaviour regarding salt consumption (WHO., 2023).

11.1. Sodium and Blood Pressure Medication

A recent meta-analysis indicates that combining a calcium channel blocker with hydrochlorothiazide is the most effective antihypertensive treatment for reducing blood pressure in salt-sensitive individuals (Qi Han et al., 2018). For patients already being treated for hypertension, effective salt reduction can help lower the number and/or doses of antihypertensive medications required (William et al., 2018). This underscores the importance of managing salt intake to enhance the efficacy of antihypertensive treatments and potentially reduce the reliance on multiple medications (Youssef et al., 2022).

11.2. Recent Recommendations from Different Guidelines

The 2020 guidelines from the International Society of Hypertension advise reducing the amount of salt used in cooking and at the table. They suggest avoiding or limiting high-salt foods such as fast foods, soy sauce, and processed foods like bread and cereals. Additionally, they recommend

population-wide initiatives to lower salt consumption and encourage the intake of fresh vegetables and fruits (Unger et al., 2020).

Similarly, the 2018 guidelines from the European Society of Cardiology and the WHO's 2020 statement recommend limiting sodium intake to less than 2 grams per day (equivalent to less than 5 grams of salt per day) for both the general population and hypertensive patients (WHO., 2020). These guidelines emphasize the importance of reducing salt added to food during cooking and meals, limiting high-salt foods, and encouraging the consumption of fresh produce. They also highlight the need for broader population-based efforts to reduce salt intake, ultimately helping to manage blood pressure and improve overall health.

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